

PLAN-B

Tackling light and noise pollution

DELIVERABLE 6.1

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

(DEC Plan) V.1

Please refer to this report as follows:
 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (DEC Plan) V.1

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List of Acronyms

DEC Plan	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (DEC Plan)
WP	Work Package
T.x.x	Task x.x
Dx.x	Deliverable x.x
CoPs	Communities of Practice
SWOT (analysis)	Strengths - Weaknesses - Opportunities- Threats
KPI's	Key Performance Indicators
TBES	Terrestrial biodiversity and ecosystems

Executive summary

The development of scientific projects on the scale of PLAN-B requires an organised plan to effectively communicate its day-to-day activities, its achievements and the dissemination of its results. It must bring its object of study (research on the impacts of light and noise pollution on terrestrial biodiversity and ecosystems (TBES)) to researchers who share it, but also to communities outside academia who are already working to protect our biodiversity, to policymakers who can influence the necessary changes to address the growing concerns, and to the public who contribute to the achievement of darker and quieter ecosystems.

Project communication must be structured, meaningful, and driven by measurable objectives that are aligned with the overall project objectives. From these needs arises this communication plan that covers all the relevant aspects of a communication strategy for this type of projects from the definition of audiences, objectives and messages, the design of the chronogram, the establishment of the actions to be carried out, the performance indicators and the possible corrective measures to be used if the path goes wrong and the expected results are not obtained.

Related documents

[\[PLAN-B\] Communication Activities form](#)

[\[PLAN-B\] Communication & dissemination Resources form](#)

[\[PLAN-B\] Collaborative environment \(Miro Board\)](#)

[\[PLAN-B\] Visual Identity Manual](#)

PLAN-B Family Picture. Kick-off meeting, Ghent (January 2024)

1. PLAN-B summary

The 'PLAN-B' project aims to address the impacts of light and noise pollution on terrestrial biodiversity. The primary objective of the project is to deepen the understanding of the impacts of light and noise pollution on the terrestrial environment and biodiversity and propose adequate measures to address these negative impacts.

PLAN-B will deploy regulatory, social, environmental, planning and technological solutions, creating a methodological framework and an open-access database for assessing the global impacts of light and noise pollution.

2. Object of the Deliverable

The aim of this deliverable is to lay the foundations for effective communication of the PLAN-B project through the elaboration of its communication plan, as well as set the grounds for the future dissemination and exploitation of the project results.

This plan, which will count on the collaboration of all the members of the consortium during its implementation, will provide them with the necessary tools for the definition of the audiences to which the project needs to address, an activities chronogram and the needed tools for the dissemination of the project's achievements, its day-to-day.

This plan will become the guide for further tasks inside the WP6, such as the set of the CoPs (Communities of Practice) and it will help to disseminate the project activities in the project piloting areas.

3. Introduction and Initial Analysis

The current version of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (DEC Plan) is mainly a document or roadmap that will be used by the consortium to plan and execute all the communication actions of the project. It will include the tools and the calendar of communication actions.

The following document aims to be a transversal tool and a framework for the project communication activities, useful for all the members of its consortium. The first version of this plan will be ready by month 6 (June 2024) and its updated version will be presented by month 18 (June 2025).

The activities included in this DEC plan, as well as the tools to carry them out, will be aligned with the overall activity of the project and will facilitate the achievement of its objectives.

WP6 Tasks and Deliverables:

T6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation, plan and project media presence	M1-M48	D6.1 Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation including Communication Activities (DECP)	M6
		D6.2 Revised Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation, including Communication Measures (DEC Plan)	M18
		D6.3 Report on the Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation Activities	M24
		D6.4 Second Report on the Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation Activities	M48
T6.2 Citizen science: Stakeholder mapping, engagement and resources to boost participation	M1-M6		
T6.3 Establishment and coordination of communities of practice (CoPs) and citizen scientists	M1-M48		
T6.4 Clustering & Outreaching activities	M1-M48		

Table 1: WP6 Tasks and Deliverables

An initial analysis of the project communications tools and assets is necessary to elaborate a consistent strategy, aligned with the overall project objectives.

The use of SWOT as an analysis tool will allow us to know the initial state of the project and will facilitate the establishment of its objectives.

This analysis will make it possible to:

- Have a first approach to the general objectives of the project and tailor the communication ones,
- Understand the tools that each consortium member makes available to the project to achieve communication objectives,
- Know communication strategies and communities around similar initiatives, to set future synergies and alliances.

SWOT Analysis:

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESS
<p>Experience in managing communication plans on previous European projects.</p> <p>The consortium has expert researchers in each of the project's areas of work.</p> <p>Possibility to publish the scientific articles produced by the consortium members.</p>	<p>The workload can make it difficult to spend time on communication tasks.</p> <p>Existence of long periods of internal inactivity in the project that do not allow the extraction of direct information for external communication.</p> <p>Work packages with little communication experience</p>
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<p>Light and noise pollution are in line with the European Green Deal and with the objectives of the EU biodiversity strategy for 2030.</p> <p>There is a wide network of organisations and institutions working on the mitigation of light and noise pollution impacts, with extensive experience in engagement and communication across Europe.</p> <p>There is direct contact with sister projects. This will help develop common communication strategies to reach larger audiences.</p>	<p>Failure to achieve the KPIs set out in the proposal.</p>

Table 2: SWOT Analysis

The collection of the information necessary to elaborate this communication plan was done through several meetings with members of the coordinating team, as well as with those responsible for the work packages and members of the consortium with experience in communication tasks.

At the beginning of the project, the communication team shared with the consortium a [form](#) to know the experience of its members in communication tasks, as well as to know the tools that each member could put at the disposal of the project to communicate and disseminate its activity.

This 'first community' has served to:

- Identify the profiles within the consortium that can be part of the communication team.
- Collect the communication tools available to each member of the consortium -websites, social media profiles, newsletters, etc.
- Raise awareness of the project among the consortium members' environment, and start building a community interested in the project.
- Following the analysis of the feedback received through the SWOT analysis, initial measures were put in place to minimise the possible negative impact on the project's communication strategy.
- Once the visual image of the project was agreed upon, the frequency of meetings was reduced to avoid overloading the consortium members, moving from a weekly to a monthly meeting.
- For operational reasons, a task force with responsibility for communication tasks was created, comprising work package leaders and consortium members with experience in communication tasks.

Work began on an editorial calendar of online publications to maintain a constant presence on social media, in which each member of the consortium can participate.

4. Setting up the DEC Plan

4.1 Visual Image Development

The visual image is the set of graphic resources that will be used to create the brand of the project, with a specific and recognisable look and feel.

This set is composed of the logo, graphic resources, colours, typography and styles, together with a user manual of all these tools for use in any of the communication activities carried out by the project, both online (infographics, documents, images, etc.) and offline (signage, events, roll-ups, flyers, etc.).

Logotype

According to previous work done by the Ibercivis design team (Nov 2023 - Jan 2024), a first draft of the project visual image was presented in the kick-off meeting (Jan 2024), with two logotype suggestions to be discussed.

Figure 1: First Drafts for logo development

Figure 2: First two proposals of logotypes

During the presentation of this first version of the logo, members of the consortium presented a series of suggestions that were accepted to achieve a result coherent with the spirit of the project.

The PLAN-B logotype has 2 pieces: icon and typography:

Figure 3: The PLAN-B logotype

Figure 4: The PLAN-B logotype variations

The icon is integrated into a rectangular shape. It represents a moth symbolizing the concept of biodiversity, which is being affected by a very close light source and a sound wave.

These sources refer to light pollution and noise pollution. In this way, both types of pollution are impacting the moth, which remains the only passive element in the logo's ensemble.

The font is placed on a line, and it is separated into 2 words: "Plan" and "B". One of these parts is highlighted with a green tone.

In addition to the design of the project logo, a complete visual identity manual for the project has been drawn up, specifying the rest of the elements of PLAN-B's corporate identity: the typefaces used, the colour palette and the rest of the graphic elements, as well as the correct uses for their implementation in all the communication actions in which the project's image is present.

Colour palette

This colour palette is warm and friendly to attract the user and create harmony between the logo and them.

To create this warm palette greenish and yellow tones have been chosen. They have the connotations: of nature, serenity, luminosity, joy, biodiversity and light.

It also has darker colours, such as purple and violet, to evoke the night and contrast with the yellow tone, as it is its complementary colour. These tones reinforce relaxation, trust and creativity.

Figure 5: The PLAN-B colour palette

Typography

The typography used for the logo is a geometric and rounded font based on its main family, **Haboro Sans**.

The endings of this font have a wide variety of weights and options, and its appearance gives it a friendly and contemporary touch. Being a sans-serif font, it allows a clear reading on screen and any paper.

This is also thanks to the openness of its eyes and the spacing between characters.

With such remarkable isotypes, it was necessary to find a simple typography that would not take too much attention away from the focus of the graphic image. That is why this font is a great choice to complete the set of the imagotype.

Specifically, the style chosen for the logo is *Haboro Soft Ext*, an extended variant of *Haboro Soft* that has greater kerning and width in its characters. The applications of this font would be the logo and titles.

Figure 6: The PLAN-B typographies

Quicksand is a free font from Google Fonts, and it is a display sans serif with rounded terminals. It is designed for display purposes but kept legible enough to use in small sizes as well. In this case, Quicksand will be used in the body text for the website and documents.

The **Oxygen** is a sans-serif font with straight and condensed endings. It works well in all graphical user interfaces, desktops and devices. This font was chosen to create contrast with the Quicksand font and will be used in headings on the web and in documents.

The [visual identity manual](#) is available to all members of the consortium, as well as the logo in all formats, including jpg., png., svg., and other variants, full colour, monochrome, white and black.

Figure 7: The PLAN-B logotype mock-ups and applications

4.2. Communication Objectives

In this initial phase (M1 – M6) of defining the communication objectives for the project, we have used the general objectives outlined in the project proposal and the Grant Agreement. It is essential that all communication objectives are aligned with these overarching goals.

Furthermore, many of these objectives are already defined through the indicators reflected in the proposal. Their achievement will be a direct objective of this communication plan.

In general terms, the definition of communication objectives will follow the SMART criteria (Specific, Measurable, Achievable and Time-bound), and each of these objectives will be accompanied by an indicator reflecting their achievement.

Some of these communication objectives are:

Documentation of the project activity on its website
Number of graphic resources generated for communication and dissemination
Presence of the project on social media
Presence of the project in traditional media
Attendance to the proposed activities
Creation and maintenance of an online community around the project

Table 3: The PLAN-B Key Objectives

To achieve these objectives, a series of indicators are defined that can be monitored during the project. Their periodic review will measure the success of the communication plan and will serve to propose corrective measures when and where necessary.

These indicators will be defined in section 5.4 of this document.

4.3. Definition of public(s)

The definition of the target audiences to which the project communication is addressed is closely related to the stakeholders identified in the proposal, as well as in the Communities of Practice (CoPs) that will be assembled during the piloting phase of the project.

These communities that the project wants to impact were defined, in principle, both in the project proposal and in the Grant Agreement, so the communication plan has a solid basis for defining its audiences, which would be:

TARGET AUDIENCES:

Public authorities , including regulatory bodies, decision- and policymakers (at local, national and European level)
Private sector , lighting and acoustic professional industry associations
Academia , researchers in light Pollution, noise pollution and biodiversity
Environmental NGOs
European-funded sister projects
Media
Civil society

Table 4: The PLAN-B Target Audiences

 The power of the CoPs as public in the communication strategy:

Local communities of quadruple helix stakeholders (including public authorities, private companies generating light and noise pollution, local researchers, NGOs and citizens) will identify citizens to gather them together in CoPs.

These CoPs will be groups of people who share a concern or passion for a particular field and learn how to improve their practice through regular interaction. Harnessing the potential for communication and dissemination of the activities of each pilot location by the members of the CoPs will be a priority for the communication strategy, and their members will be persuaded to become micro-influencers / prescribers of the project.

4.4. Key Messages

Successful communication requires tailoring messages to the identified audiences while remaining aligned with the communication objectives and overall project objectives.

During the elaboration of the communication plan, work will be done on the design of these messages, which will serve as a guide for the communication actions to be carried out with each specific audience.

One phrase simply delivers the message “what do we do” to specific targeted audiences.

As a first approximation, we can compile some of these messages:

KEY MESSAGES:

Scientific evidence and data will help you to improve light and noise pollution strategies.
Better light design for better quality of the environment for the terrestrial biodiversity and ecosystems.
Findings and actions to reduce light and noise pollution will get you involved and participate in the next actions to reduce their impacts.
Get involved in tackling light and noise pollution in your community
PLAN-B develops a framework for assessing light and noise pollution impacts to inform environmental decision-making.
PLAN-B develops an open-access database on light and noise impacts on terrestrial biodiversity.

Table 5: The PLAN-B Key Messages

📌 To achieve agreement on the definition of the key messages, a [collaborative space](#) was opened where members of the communication team could make their contributions and validate the appropriateness of the results.

📌 Using the [collaborative space](#), it has been possible to establish relationships between the project’s target audiences, the key messages that PLAN-B wants to convey and the actions that will be carried out to disseminate them. These actions will be presented in the following sections of this document.

Figure 8: Key Messages and their relationships with target audiences and communication actions

(source: [PLAN-B Miro board](#))

5. Communication Action Plan

5.1. Internal communication

The complexity of a project such as PLAN-B, in which researchers and professionals from different countries must coordinate different tasks and work groups, with different timetables, languages and customs, requires the implementation of effective internal communication tools that facilitate the correct flow of information and enable meetings when carrying out team tasks.

For this reason, a series of tools have been implemented to enable communication between members, share documentation and create spaces in which to work asynchronously, facilitating the achievement of their objectives.

These internal communication tools are coordinated through an internal communication plan that helps to keep all members of the consortium up to date with the development of the project, as well as to maintain a positive atmosphere aligned with the general objectives of the project.

SharePoint as a common space for project documentation and communication

The University of Ghent, as the coordinating entity of the project, has provided space for the management of the documents generated by the project and is responsible for their custody. The space is managed through **SharePoint Server** (Microsoft), a place to store, organise, share and access information from any device. All the members of the consortium have access to this space, which is organised around the different work packages that make up the project. There is also space for chats between members, notes and reminders about milestones and appointments.

Work packages regular meetings

To facilitate communication within and between the different work packages, share the status of the tasks performed and exchange experiences and knowledge, a calendar of online meetings has been planned through the **Microsoft Teams** tool. Its planning is variable and is adjusted to the needs and the moment in which each work package is, being able to be weekly or monthly.

In addition, the project coordination team plans **general assemblies** every six months to assess the progress of the project, discuss ongoing work, plan future steps, exchange updates and reconnect with all stakeholders responsible for each work package. These meetings can be online or face-to-face, and external advisory boards are invited to hear

first-hand about the progress of the project and share their expertise with the consortium.

Online communication tools for the consortium

The exchange of information between consortium members is done through **mailing lists** that allow a direct and bidirectional flow of information between consortium members. Both a general mailing list and work-package-specific mailing lists have been created.

In the SharePoint environment, **templates** have been introduced to standardise the look and feel of the documents produced by the project, following the guidelines of the project's visual image. Thus, every member has layouts available for use in text documents and presentations, both inside and outside the project.

In the early stages of the project, the communication team designed three tools to implement this plan for the project:

The [Communication & dissemination Resources form](#) which helped to find out the communication resources of the consortium members and integrate them into the communication plan.

The [communication activities form](#), a tool for collecting all the milestones achieved by the project and which is used as a direct communication channel between each member of the project and the communication team. This form allows to know the status of the activities of each work package in an easy and useful way, as well as the presence of the project in activities such as congresses, the publication of articles and in short, any activity that must be collected and disseminated to the community around the project.

A [collaborative space](#) in the online tool Miro in which to work collaboratively and asynchronously on the initial tasks of the communication plan: the definition of objectives, audiences and messages to be transmitted by the project, as well as the initial SWOT analysis.

Website and blog as a register and starting point for the communication strategy.

All the communication tools at the service of the consortium converge on the [project's website](#), which serves as a repository of PLAN-B's activity and a showcase for its achievements.

Thus, all communication actions, from the hosting of deliverables, the publication of articles, the call for activities, the dissemination of results or the presence of PLAN-B in social media, start on the website, which is regularly fed by the content generated by the consortium and collected in the form.

The project's website as lighthouse for the community

The website aims to become a centre for gathering information about the project's study and it will contain the state of the art of research in the relevant areas, as well as the collaboration between sister projects and institutions working in the same direction as the project. The website also includes information about the advisory board members.

Thus, the PLAN-B website will become not only a reflection of the development of the project but also a key actor in promoting the work and the connection between similar initiatives that want to share their work and achievements with us.

5.2. External communication and beyond

5.2.1 The PLAN-B Content Cycle as an external communication strategy

PLAN-B's external communication strategy is structured around two axes: the constant presence of the project on social media and the dissemination of its activity through traditional media. The communication objectives sought are the creation of a community around the project and its activities, as well as raising awareness of the adverse impacts of light and noise pollution on terrestrial biodiversity and ecosystems in Europe. All content generated by the project will reach its target audience through the following cycle:

Figure 9: The PLAN-B Content Cycle

We count on the one hand, as primary sources of information on the project the activity of the work packages: **the achievement of their objectives, the development of their studies, the publication of results, the organisation of pilot activities, etc.** On the other hand, all the activities carried out by the consortium members, as listed in the activity form: presence at conferences and other clustering activities, publication of articles, collection of news related to the object of study of the project, etc.

All this information is posted on the website's blog and serves as a tool for disseminating the project through social networks and sharing relevant content with our community. The aim of this information trail is to attract traffic and visits to the project's website and increase its visibility on social media, reinforcing the existing communities in each social network in which PLAN-B is present.

The collection of relevant project information on the blog also allows us to easily prepare **the project's newsletter**, which will be launched during M7, and which will include the highlights of the project's activity over the last few weeks for dissemination via email. This newsletter is planned to be published quarterly and, as with the publication on social networks, its publication encourages traffic back to the project's website.

The cycle of the content collected on the website ends with its dissemination in traditional media, which can be accessed through press releases, interviews with researchers and the dissemination of the relevant results of the project.

Social media presence

After the initial analysis and definition of the target audiences the project wanted to address, it was decided to open profiles on the social networks where they are present: **LinkedIn and X/Twitter**. This allowed us to reach out to established communities dealing with the key issues of the project -dark sky associations, naturalists, experts, activists, NGOs, as well as researchers, policymakers and the general public. The previous experience of several consortium members in these communities helped us first to raise awareness of the project and then, to share our activities.

This analysis carried out with the information collected from the consortium members through the initial [form](#), showed that most of them were present on these social networks. Posting and sharing by tagging our members' profiles ensures that we reach their established communities.

https://x.com/Planb_team

<https://linkedin.com/plan-b-project-eu>

5.2.2 Editorial Content Calendar

The editorial calendar is the tool we have chosen to establish the content strategies for the blog, as it brings together the workflow in terms of content types, authors and publication dates.

During the first stage of the project the project's communication team, responsible for WP6, was in charge of writing, editing and publishing the blog entries together with the

coordinating team, giving time to elaborate the editorial calendar, ready for the M6. The sources of content to create the blogposts have been defined by their cycle (Fig. 8):

- Research articles,
- Day to Day Activities
- Chronicles of appearance in congresses and clustering activities
- Publication of deliverables
- Achievement of milestones
- Project information
- Project events.

First, the requirements that each blog must have been defined:

Blogpost TITLE	
WHO is responsible?	WP leader Task Leader Article author Activity manager
WHEN is published?	According to the editorial calendar
WHAT is it about?	Description
Who is the TARGET AUDIENCE	Public authorities Private sector Academia Environmental NGOs European-funded sister projects Media Civil society
CALL TO ACTION	Link to website Join the community Share content on social media Join project activity

Table 6: The PLAN-B Blogpost definition

Once the content is created in the webpage blog, we draw up the editorial calendar which reflects the publication date on the website and the publication dates on the project's social media profiles. From M6 and throughout the rest of the project, the author of the content -package leader, tasks leader, author or contributor- will receive instructions to include its publication in the editorial calendar or will be asked to create the content defined in this calendar.

With the editorial calendar, we ensure, on the one hand, the registration of the project's activity and, on the other hand, a constant flow of information in social networks that allows us to strengthen a community interested in the issues that the project works on and in participating in its activities.

	March 2024			April 2024				
	Week 3	Week 4	Week 5	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3	Week 4	Week 5
blogpost		Project presentation	Catholic Easter holidays	Wps presentation (I)	Wps presentation (II)	Wps presentation (III)		What is light pollution
rrss	Consortium members (I)	Consortium members (II)	Catholic Easter holidays	Consortium members (III)				
		Project presentation	Catholic Easter holidays	Wps presentation (I)	Wps presentation (II)	Wps presentation (III)		

Table 7: The PLAN-B content calendar (sample / monthly)

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
1	Day	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Saturday		NOTES
2	Date	22/04/2024	23/04/2024	24/04/2024	25/04/2024	26/04/2024	27/04/2024		Insert the date
3	Content Assignee	Gdansk Team			Yana				Responsible for delivering content WP lead
4	Post Assignee	Daniel	Daniel	Daniel	Daniel	Daniel	Daniel		Member of IBERCIVIS
5	status	published			scheduled				
6	link to text	email sent			email sent				
7	Category			PLAN-B activities		PLAN-B activities			Content categories are indicated on the first page of this document. Please, choose the category accordingly.
8	What is the post about?			Gdansk meeting (18-19/04/2024) chronicle		Yana's participation in podcast presenting PLAN-B			Write post description or add text which should be published or give a link to the relevant research/policy publication.
9	blog link	https://plan-b-project.eu/2024/04/24/gdnask-meeting-recap/							
10	twitter copy								suggestion of twitter publication. 280 characters maximum. suggestion of LinkedIn publication. Please add @members to be tagged in the final publication (researchers profiles, institutions, members of the consortium, sister projects, etc)
11	LinkedIn copy								suggestion of LinkedIn publication. Please add @members to be tagged in the final publication (researchers profiles, institutions, members of the consortium, sister projects, etc)
12	Hashtags					#lightpollution	#darkskyprotection		Always add hashtags with regard to the post category. For example, if the content is about Light Pollution (LP) add hashtags: #lightpollution #darkskyprotection
13									

Table 8: The PLAN-B content calendar (sample / weekly)

The project's communication team has tools for programming the publications in the social media profiles, as well as to know the impact on the community, through the analytics provided by [Google](#) and [Metricool](#).

These metrics will serve to know the level of achievement of the **key indicators of success and performance** of the communication strategies (KPIs) and allow us to monitor and establish corrective measures when necessary.

5.3 Offline Activities (synergies with sister projects)

Within the WP6 activities there are three tasks focused on the consolidation of communities around the project:

- T6.2 Citizen science: Stakeholder mapping, engagement and resources to boost participation
- T6.3 Establishment and coordination of communities of practice (CoPs) and citizen scientists
- T6.4 Clustering & Outreaching activities

These are closely related to the communication strategies of this plan. On the one hand, the stakeholder mapping carried out initially (T6.2) has allowed a more precise definition of the audiences to be addressed by the project and has identified communities with which to establish CoPs (T6.3). In addition, initial contacts with sister projects have allowed us to map out joint communication strategies, both to share common content and to design joint clustering activities to amplify the effect of Task 6.4.

To align the communication objectives of our sister projects, regular meetings have been planned, in which the development of common communication materials - flyers, infographics, web space, publications and joint events - has been agreed upon to amplify the effect of communication and multiply its reach. PLAN-B meetings with the [AquaPlan](#) and [Interreg - Darker Sky](#) projects have laid solid foundations for future inter-project collaborations.

5.4 Review, reassess and refine. KPI's and corrective measurements

To measure the success of this communication plan, a series of indicators (KPIs) are defined to show the degree of achievement of the actions carried out. These quantitative indicators were largely defined in the project proposal and in the Grant Agreement, and their achievement will contribute to the overall success of the project.

These are the initial indicators that will be used to measure the degree of achievement of the project's communication objectives.

Objective	Indicator KPI
Documentation of the project activity on its website	Blog Posts: 30 Web: 10000 views
Number of graphic resources generated for communication and dissemination	Policy Briefs: 3 (D4.2, D4.3, D4.4) Infographics: 3
Presence of the project on social media	Twitter/X: 1000 followers LinkedIn: 300 followers
Presence of the project in traditional media	Media appearances: 20
Attendance to the proposed activities	Final Conference: 150 attendees
Creation and maintenance of an online community around the project	Newsletter: 100 followers / 1 newsletter per quarter

Table 9: The PLAN-B objectives and indicators (KPIs)

Some figures from M2 to M6:

	3600 impressions 1300 visits
	17 posts 1 post/week
	53 following / 122 followers / 59 posts Reach: 5112 impressions
	109 followers / 18 posts Reach: 3170 impressions

Table 10: The PLAN-B figures resume (M2 to M6)

The figures obtained so far show an optimistic outlook for the following months of the project. However, the monthly meetings of the communication team, together with the reviews carried out by the coordinating team and the general assemblies, will enable new communication actions to be established that will facilitate the achievement of its objectives.

Any deviation in this path and the implementation of corrective measures will be duly analysed and reported in the second edition of this communication plan, foreseen for M18.